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DENTAL ANTHROPOLOGY: A BRIEF DEFINITION

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Resumen

Académicamente la Antropología Dental se ubica dentro de los estudios de *Biología Ósea Humana* (Lukacs, 1997) u *Osteología Étnica*. Su objetivo principal es reconocer los atributos en la forma de los dientes que nos puedan ayudar a *recrear* dinámicas bioculturales de las poblaciones humanas relacionadas especialmente con el *Estado de Salud – Enfermedad*, las *Costumbres Alimenticias* y las *Transformaciones Microevolutivas*, vinculados estos últimos a la *Etnogénesis* de los pueblos actuales y pasados. Este artículo pretende introducir al lector en los campos principales de la disciplina desde un punto de vista Teórico.

Abstract

Dental Anthropology is Academically located within the human bone biology studies (Lukacs, 1997) or Ethnic Osteology. Its main goal is to recognize attributes in the teeth form which can help us create biocultural dynamics of human populations specifically related to Health–Illness State, Feeding Habits and Microevolutionary Transformations, related themselves to the ethnogenesis of current and ancient times. This article is intended to introduce the reader in the main fields of the discipline from a theoretical point of view.

Introduction

A. Zoubov (1997) defines Dental Anthropology as the study of morphological and metrical variation of dentition in human populations, according to time and space; in relation to feeding changes which have produced evolutionary processes in the human beings. John R. Lukacs (1997) considers Dental Anthropology as the science about the tooth, which determines diet patterns, physiological stress levels, biological affinities and migration patterns in ancient populations.

This science allows anthropologists to explain the human beings diversity and adaptation.

C. Spencer Larsen and M. Kelly (1991) define Dental Anthropology as the study of tooth size and form. This allows us to establish phylogenetic, evolutionary and adaptable relations within ethnographic, forensic and ecological contexts. S. Hillson (1996) defines Dental Anthropology simply as the discipline concerned about studying people and their biocultural behavior, by using evidences provided by their teeth.

This science involves six (6) research topics: *Morphology* which is the widest and most explored research field since the middle of the 19th century. It attempts to phenetically characterize human populations with taxonomic and comparative aims within spatial and temporal scales, trying to recreate the behavior of human microevolutionary dynamics (Hillson, 1986; Minkov, 1996; Zoubov, 1997). *Odontometry* establishes relations among dental dimensions and the sexual dimorphism and in a wider temporal range, it is related to dietary transformation, trajectories and movements of the population that involve the evolutionary history of humanity (Brace, 1981). *Dental Wear* especially emphasizes dietary reconstruction and approximate calculations of the age at death (Molnar, 1971; Smith, 1984, 1991; Lovejoy, 1985; Bass, 1995). *Dental Pathology* lets us obtain illness adaptability indicators and their relations with demographic custom patterns, feeding deficiencies and forms of biocultural adaptation to pathogenic control (Goodman *et al.*, 1987; Goodman and Rose, 1990; Lukacs, 1989, 1997). *Dental Growth and Development* explains the body ontogenic processes in relation to sex, age, feeding, and specific pathologies and processes (Demirjian *et al.*, 1973; Ubelaker, 1989). And finally *Cultural Treatments* that leave impressions in the tooth form, indicate habits related to ornamentations, oral hygiene, and surgical practices (Romero,

1974; Ubelaker, 1989).

This collection of fields lets us go deeper in, and contribute to, the knowledge of three wide anthropological aspects. 1) *Health-Illness State*, which deals with both biological and cultural dynamics, which provoke and control the stressor behavior from infectious, nutritional, genetic or degenerative origin; the way they are consciously or unconsciously formed, manifested and controlled by human populations, by means of biocultural strategies. 2) *Diet* which deals with the obtention, preparation and food ingestion frequency processes and its relation to daily feeding habits. And 3) *Microevolutionary Transformations*, which deal with the sociocultural processes that control the genetic flow's spatial-temporal dynamics, manifested in human populations phenetic dimensions.

The Biocultural Perspective

During the last century, Physical Anthropology used to proclaim the study of human biological variability, explained from the evolutionary perspective (Wienker, 1997). This only allowed to know biological aspects of human populations. Nowadays, Bioanthropology pretends to study human diversity and explain it from a biocultural perspective, which lets us know systems and relations among biological and cultural aspects, and better understand, transformations of human conditions through space and time (Pucciarelli, 1994; Marcellino, 1994). For the renowned bioanthropologist Jack Kelso (1997), the biocultural perspective is composed of interdependent relations among three main aspects: 1) Human Biology; 2) Culture; and 3) Nature, in human groups. The individual and collective configurations and significances, among these aspects, are particular to each population and constitute components of their totality. They are directly and indirectly expressed in their bones and tooth form.

In this context, Dental Anthropology develops its approximations to the knowledge of ancient and present human populations. The rule is to know the human being through the tooth study and not in the way it used to be done, knowing the human teeth and the functional relations with the material culture. In other words, the tooth is used as a means to know the human populations biocultural dynamics.

In this way, the biocultural perspective becomes the theoretical shelter that allows us to explain and know human populations from what we observe in their bones and teeth, and not the other way around.

Topics

Morphology

Dental Morphology is used in two ways: the first way is as a general morphology to classify kinds of teeth

(deciduous and permanent incisors, canines, premolars, and molars). This helps us identify the minimum number of individuals (MNI) when we find isolated teeth. The second way is a special morphology, which allows us to characterize populations, establish biological distances, and estimate genetic flow trajectories through time and space. There are some classification systems to systematically register, these special characteristics in the tooth form, such as the ASU (Turner *et al*, 1991), or the Russian System (Zoubov, 1997).

Odontometry

The establishment of metric referents that lets us compare dental form dimensions is used in three ways: the first way is a help for sex identification in remains that come from forensic and archaeological contexts (Ditch and Rose, 1972). The second way is used as a means of comparison among populations to estimate biological relationships (Brace, 1981). And the third way is used as a representation of the diet transformations in hominids (Wolpoff, 1971).

Paleopathology

The diagnoses of oral illnesses of genetic, infectious, and degenerative kind is used with two objectives: the first is to establish illnesses dispersion models. That is, the way they behave evolutionarily through time and space, and how they influence the death causes of human populations (Verano and Ubelaker, 1996). The second is to establish intentional or unintentional indicators of adaptations to this pathogens.

Dental Wear

The progressive loss of dental enamel is related to three processes: the first is Individual Age (Zoubov 1968; Lovejoy, 1985; Ubelaker, 1989); the second is the abrasiveness of Diet; and the third is the use that individuals make of their teeth for purposes different from their diet (Molnar, 1972). The dental wear is also used as a way of characterizing populations and making interpopulation comparisons (Smith, 1984, 1991).

Cultural Treatments

The relevance or importance that human groups give to their teeth as well as the representativity and meaning that teeth and their modifications can take in a community are both anthropological aspects that have not been sufficiently studied and attempted to systematize (Romero, 1974).

Conclusions

We may consider Dental Anthropology as a morphological and systematic science that studies the Biocultural Diversity of Ancient and Present Human Populations in its double dimension, spatial and temporal,

through the study and analysis of the dental system.

The human tooth analysis permits us to observe aspects directly related to the socio-cultural tooth use and function as well as behavioral and physiological functions occurred in the biocultural daily life of a human population.

Throughout the research process developed by Dental Anthropology it is possible to solve general problems of anthropological type, like the ones related to the origin, settlement, movement, adaptation, and contact of human groups in space and time.

In general, Dental Anthropology refers to all the hereditary, dietary, pathological, hygienic and ornamental aspects expressed in the tooth form, and which let us infer aspects about the behavior and adaptations linked to the evolutionary process of ancient and present human populations. Thanks to the characteristics of the discipline, it is possible to reconstruct and prospect behavior related to the population dynamics.

In summary, a tooth can provide individual and group information on the dynamic relations occurred between the Biology-Culture dichotomy and indicate human group adaptability processes.

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